

Preparation of Thioureopentacyanoferrate(II) anion

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Received 25 March 1971.

Six coordinated mono substituted pentacyanoferrate(II) anion having the general formula $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{CN})_5\text{L}] (3+n)^-$ (where $n = 0, \pm 1$ or 2 depending upon the nature of L) are known of wide variety¹. Fearon² showed that pentacyanoammine ferrate gives a blue colour with thiourea. Feigl³ observed that this colour reaction can be utilized to identify thiourea in microquantities. The present paper describes the isolation of thioureopentacyanoferrate (II) anion.

Powdered sodium nitroprusside (3.0 g) was dissolved in minimum volume of methanol and mixed with slightly greater than stoichiometric amount of sodium hydroxide (0.9 g) dissolved in methanol and gently refluxed on a boiling waterbath for 30 mins. when whole of the nitroprusside was converted into nitrito compound. This was suction filtered and dissolved in minimum volume of aqueous methanol (1 : 2 ratio). Slightly greater than one equivalent of thiourea (1.0 g) was added to it dissolved in methanol and the mixture was refluxed for 3 hrs. on a boiling waterbath, when the yellow solution of the nitrito compound changed to deep reddish violet. The reaction is found to be catalysed by sunlight and in the presence of traces of alkali. The resulting solution was cooled and excess of methanol was added and stirred vigorously when crimson coloured solid precipitated out. This was suction filtered, dissolved in water and reprecipitated by adding methanol. This process was repeated till the washliquor was free from nitrite (tested by Griess solution) and was dried in vacuum desiccator over conc. H_2SO_4 to constant weight and analysed.

Found : Na, 19.52; Fe, 16.20; N, 28.31; S, 9.65; $\text{Na}_3[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{CN})_5\text{SC}(\text{NH}_2)_2]$, H_2O requires : Na, 19.78; Fe, 16.02; N, 28.09; S, 9.46%.

This salt is hygroscopic in nature. It is very soluble in water forming an intense reddish violet colour but it is insoluble in common organic solvents. It is interesting to note that unlike $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{NOS}]^{4-}$, $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{SC}(\text{NH}_2)_2]^{3-}$ is very stable in aqueous solution. In presence of alkalies, it is quite stable even on prolonged warming but in acidic medium, rapid decomposition takes place with the liberation of HCN and separation of prussian blue. Its aqueous solution gives insoluble precipitates with the following metal ions:

Cu^{2+} (Brown), Fe^{3+} (Blue), Fe^{2+} (Pinkish brown on standing turns blue), Mn^{2+} (Pink), Ni^{2+} (Pinkish red), Ag^+ (Reddish orange), Zn^{2+} (Bright orange), Co^{2+} (Red), Pb^{2+} (Bright pink).

The corresponding potassium or ammonium salts can be made metathetically using silver salt and corresponding chloride salt in aqueous medium. The free acid can be generated by treating HCl on the Ag- salt or by passing H₂S through an aqueous suspension of Pb-salt. The acid is brown in colour and is a strong one to react with carbonates of alkali metals with effervescence to produce reddish violet salts. Thermal decomposition of the sodium salt takes place with the evolution of NH₃ first followed by the expulsion of H₂S. Br₂-water oxidises it to a transient violetish green solution but the oxidised form is unstable in this medium. However, oxidation by iodine in alcoholic solution is interesting where a green oxidised form is formed.

The salt is diamagnetic at room temperature. Infra-red spectrum (Nujol) shows, besides one CN⁻ stretching, absorption at 720 cm⁻¹ which is due to coordinated thiourea. Further studies are in progress and details will be published later. The author expresses his grateful thanks to Principal H. N. Singh of this college for providing laboratory facilities.

R E F E R E N C E S

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